

Critical perspective into the Artificial intelligence's existence in the pharmaceutical and medical fields

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ABSTRACT

"Artificial intelligence (AI) is a specialized field of computer science that enables machines to perform tasks more efficiently and understand complex data." The field of AI-focused studies has expanded rapidly, and its usage in medical treatments and academic studies are progressing at a quicker pace. This study goes into great length about the advantages and difficulties of using artificial intelligence in not only in pharmacological but also in experimental work in labs. The utilization of AI developing novel drug entities, pandemic or epidemic forecasting, personalized treatment, digital therapy, and illness diagnostics in great detail. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies currently are most in demand for neural networks and deep learning. Clinical trial design holds great promise for Bayesian nonparametric models; patient identification and trial monitoring are handled by wearable technology and natural language processing. The COVID-19, Zika, Ebola, and seasonal influenza epidemics were predicted using deep learning and neural networks. AI technology is advancing rapidly, which could lead to faster and more affordable progress in pharmaceutical and healthcare research, ultimately improving public services and benefiting the scientific community.

KEYWORDS: clinical trial, detection, artificial intelligence, analysis, discovery, outbreak, treatment, healthcare

INTRODUCTION

The artificial intelligence (AI) are the collection of different intelligent behaviours and processes produced by the simulations using computers, standards, or techniques that allow a machine to mimic mental functions that humans perform on a daily basis [1, 2]. Artificial intelligence is quickly entering the healthcare industry and profoundly impact clinical diagnosis, automation, and illness evaluation [3]. Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents potential for further exploration with respect to pharmacological and medical research because of its ability to evaluate vast volumes of data from multiple modalities [4]. Data obtained from previous research and also from recent studies tells us about the relevance of AI into medical treatment and other fields. The medical field incorporates artificial intelligence (AI) technology such as automated robotic procedures, the processing of natural languages, mechanical or physical robots, and algorithms for learning [5]. Models of neural networks and advanced machine learning along with unlike characteristics are being used in machine learning (ML) to discover clinically relevant aspects in imaging data at an early stage, especially in various carcinomas/ lymphomas diagnosis [6, 7].s Natural language processing uses algorithms for human speech analysis and its interpretation.

Machine learning approaches are rapidly being utilized NLP, or natural language processing, investigate unorganized details contained in systems as well as documents, such as lab results and doctor's notes. This mapping of crucial details from multiple pictures and written information facilitates making confirmations regarding findings and management techniques [8]. Patients now have access to individualized therapeutic approaches and a quick, accurate diagnosis because to continuous disruptive innovation [9]. AI-driven remedies have been found, such as sites that are able to employ a range of data kinds, such as imaging, biomarkers, biometrics, and symptoms that patients have reported. The ability to identify dangerous AI advancements enable early illness detection, raising the possibility that prevention will take place as a result of early diagnosis [10, 11]. Automation of robotic processes leverages readily configurable, low-cost technology to do structure digital tasks for managerial reasons and even to act as knowledgeable structure. In addition, this can be utilized in conjunction with image recognition. The healthcare system can make use of this technology for constant processes including prior authorization, patient record updates, and billing [12].

Artificial intelligence, or AI, is very important to the pharmaceutical sector because it is widely applicable at different levels of many essential procedures. It is evident that artificial intelligence affects every stage of the lifecycle of a medicinal product. Algorithms used in drug discovery include machine learning (ML), recurrent neural networks, and deep learning (RNNs), deep neural networks (DNNs), virtual screening (VS), support vector machines (SVMs), Quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSRL) technologies powered by AI, such as QSLRML and so on. Artificial intelligence (AI) biological neural networks serve as an inspiration for neural networks which process input data and provide an output after processing it. Multiple connected units are used in artificial neural networks (ANN) to handle data. DNNs and ANNs, which have data processing units with several layers are comparable. RNNs manage the information sequentially, using the outcome from one analysis to process the input for the subsequent analysis phase. Regression analysis and categorization of input data are done with SVMs. Artificial intelligence is being utilized in pharmaceutical product development to optimize the selection of development procedures, choose the appropriate excipients, and ensure compliance with all regulatory requirements. Model expert systems (MES), artificially intelligent neural networks and other technologies are used in the creation of pharmaceutical products. Artificial intelligence (AI) is utilized in production to match manufacturing faults to established limits through automated and personalized manufacturing. To attain the required quality, artificial intelligence technologies as tablet and meta classifiers are utilized [13]. Clinical trials that employ AI to pick individuals and monitor the experiment see a decrease in dropout rates as a result of the careful monitoring. Clinical studies are using machine learning [14].

The aforementioned industries have witnessed a notable increase in AI, which has enhanced the outcomes. The healthcare and pharmaceutical industries use artificial intelligence extensively; review covered the use of AI in treatment personalization, clinical trials, drug discovery, disease diagnosis, and epidemiological research for pandemic or epidemic forecasting. Research on how artificial intelligence (AI) is being used in education, market analysis, customer service, and commerce manufacturing of pharmaceuticals, customer service, or any other topic unrelated to this study does not include any research on pharmaceuticals or healthcare. Using keyword-specific searches on resources such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, and PubMed, all of the studies are located. This

review covers a wide range of significant topics, and this article goes into great detail about how artificial intelligence (AI) aids in forecasting, diagnosis, detection, discovery, and therapy.

ROLE OF AI IN DIAGNOSIS OF DISEASES

In order to ensure patients' well-being and plan a thoughtful course of intervention, disease assessment became crucial. The various errors caused by human error result in imprecise diagnoses, and misinterpreting the data generated complexity and labour to the task. By guaranteeing accuracy and efficiency, artificial intelligence (AI) is applicable to a variety of applications. After a thorough analysis of the literature, there have been presentations on the uses of varied techniques diagnosis of various ailments. Numerous environmental indicators suggest that the need for the healthcare system will only increase in tandem with the growth of the human population [15]. Even though there are delicate, contradicting, non-analysing incongruities, a substantial amount of research has demonstrated that creative methods can clarify their relevance by highlighting the scenario that hasn't been handled yet [16].

It's important to categorize patients based on how severely their illnesses have impacted them, and AI may have a greater influence on diagnosis [17]. When a person's condition is determined by particular pre-existing conditions, it is called a diagnosis [18]. Most assessments are obtained through testing and examination, so it is generally advised to maintain a record of each patient's health report forms. The majority of the information gathering's correct results are related to the medical specifications needed for timely evaluations. Physicians alone have the final say over any changes to the analysis [19]. Given that the availability of multiple diagnostic methodologies is raising trust concerns, it is therefore necessary should place greater emphasis on AI than on treatment or testing in order to determine and identify the early prognostic phases of the illness. A treatment like this can help initiate treatment early on, and treatment like this can lead to both noticeable changes in the patient and an increase in AI module efficiency [20]. These days, a significant amount of deep learning, neural networks, and algorithm-based technology would be needed to identify, extract, and use all of the collected data [21]. The two primary illnesses where AI has been used are dementia [22] and cancer become increasingly important and played a critical role [23]. The significance of the found clusters determines acceptance rather than user input [24]. It is possible to diagnose hepatitis through unsupervised learning [25]. Nonetheless, a variety of evolutionary modifications and prediction adjustments can yield deep learning connections [26]. Wider sets of data with a variety of variables can typically support AI's appropriateness [27], but the outcome is incomprehensible [28].

The categorization of dermatological disorders is one of the numerous instances of deep learning in diagnostics [29] and atrial fibrillation detection [30]. Cross-validation can be used to split data randomly across several sets in order to estimate algorithms [31]. Three crucial areas are the focus of popular AI measurements: accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity [32]. The outcomes can be produced more thoroughly by the clinical attributes such as literature analysis, support vector machines, nearest neighbours, random forests, decision trees, logistic regression, naïve Bayes, discriminate analysis, and convolution neural networks can be used to supervise neural pathways and deep learning networks. Algorithm-based, performance-driven analysis can be carried out using the training and testing samples' origin, sample size, and feature count. The identification of liver diseases involved the integration of reasoning and decision trees [33].

Several investigations were conducted on predictive modelling, and it was found to be quite effective in predicting Parkinson's disease in its early stages [34]. In order to diagnose lung diseases, chest X-ray images were used in the development of the rib segmentation technique [35]. Numerous drawbacks render traditional methods useless for rib-wise segmentation of X-ray images. Through unpaired sample augmentation of chest X-ray images of pneumonia patients, the researchers in this study have developed an algorithm, and a multi-scale network then learns the features of images. According to the study, this kind of algorithm performs well and improves rib segmentation, which may be helpful in the diagnosis of lung cancer and other lung conditions [36]. Currently, researchers have used several equipment's learning and algorithms to process ECG data in order to identify and categorize heart arrhythmias. In a different study, TB [37] was diagnosed and classified utilizing the support vector machine (SVM) classifier and the genetic algorithm for optimization (GA).

ROLE OF AI IN DIGITAL TREATMENT AND PERSONALIZED HEALING

Artificial intelligence (AI) can identify important relationships in the raw datasheets that lead to potential applications in disease diagnosis, treatment, and mitigation. It is possible to apply many of the more modern methods employed in this rapidly developing field of computational knowledge to practically any area of medical study. It takes a lot of knowledge to tackle the difficult clinical problems; this knowledge must be acquired, evaluated, and applied. The advancement of AI in medicine has aided medical professionals in managing challenging patient issues. Healthcare workers can work with data more effectively by utilizing systems like fuzzy expert systems, hybrid intelligent systems, artificial neural networks, and evolutionary computing [38]. Artificial neural networks are based on the organic nervous system. These networks are made up of linked computer processors that are able to use calculations to process inputs in parallel [39]. A binary threshold function was used to produce the first artificial neuron. The most widely used multilayer feed-forward perceptron model had three layers: input, middle, and output. There are forty neural connections total, with a weight assigned to each neuron [40].

ROLE OF AI IN RADIO IMAGING TECHNOLOGY

An extremely helpful relatively-new technique for radiation treatment planning is programmed prophylaxis preparation. Programmed prophylaxis preparation greatly improves the plan's excellence, reliability, and chances of mistake. Disease management can be categorized into three groups: multi-criteria optimization, automated rule implementation, and reasoning modelling of prior knowledge in clinical practice [41]. Simple automated computer programs with structures can be used to carry out the clinical recommendations.

Programmed prophylaxis preparation may measure not only physiological but also anatomical parameters or vitals for disease detection. Additionally, it can mimic the thought processes that are commonly used in medical treatment planning. Accuracy has been demonstrated in three-dimensional dosage distribution and dose models for spatial dosage [42]. Radiomics provides comprehensive information about malignancies by utilizing a range of imaging biomarkers. Radiomics is a useful tool for predicting the effects and toxicity of radiation therapy on individual patients [43].

ROLE OF AI IN CYTOTOXICITY

Gene expression data was used to train an artificial neural network to find new prognostic markers for MCL. The results showed that 58 genes exhibited highly accurate survival predictions, with 10 genes linked to poor survival and 5 genes associated with favourable survival number [45]. Three genes were correlated with poor survival and four genes with good survival for DLBCL patients [46], according to a multivariate analysis of gene expression using the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). Gene expression data was used to train an artificial neural network to find new prognostic markers for MCL [47]. The results showed that 58 genes exhibited highly accurate survival predictions, with 10 genes linked to poor survival and 5 genes associated with favourable survival. DLBCL patients have a multivariate analysis of gene expression using the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) revealed a correlation between three genes and poor survival and four genes and good survival [48].

Colorectal cancer (CRC) screening technology is employed in gastrointestinal cancer to assess the cancerous invasion in patients [49], and visual nocturnal surveillance for *Helicobacter pylori* infection is a critical factor in predicting the advancement of gastric cancer [50], endoscopic imaging, and appropriate blood testing can all help detect cancer early and slow its spread. Inevitably, because to a lack of suitable blinded controlled studies and randomization, only retroactive evidence can be gathered in AI [51]. Furthermore, in a number of studies, the prediction models did not support the malignant prognosis. The Cox Survival Regression Algorithm, Random Survival Forest Algorithm, and Multi-Task Logistic Regression Algorithm are among the models that have now gained multiple dimensions and plausible predictive outcomes [52]. These advancements have made it possible to computerize the diagnosis of malignancy in gastroenterology. This includes the ability to classify cases and perform endocytoscopy-based detection and magnification, which is a method not yet used in clinical practice [53]. Over the previous ten years, AI has shown significant promise in the identification of breast cancer. Even before neo adjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) is started, patients with breast cancer can have their treatment response predicted using AI-assisted approaches, which combine quantitative and qualitative MRI data.

The benefit of artificial intelligence is its potential for application in lesion detection, segmentation, and classification; breast density evaluation; and breast cancer risk assessment. AI-based technologies can reduce the possibility that false-negative mammograms will be interpreted and assist radiologists in making more accurate diagnoses of benign and malignant breast lesions [54]. The progress made in this approach is still in its early stages and has several drawbacks, among these are the scarcity of large-scale publicly available datasets, the requirement for high-resolution images, the dependence on ROI annotations, problems with binary classification as well as the incapacity to manage several tasks concurrently. Because there aren't enough sufficient public data sets to train deep convolution neural networks (DCNNs), the development of AI tools, like DL-based CAD, has remained in its early stages [55].

ROLE OF AI IN OPHTHMOLOGY

High-resolution retinal imaging has revolutionized the monitoring of human health. A single retinal image can provide highly personalized data, and when combined with advanced precision medicine, an ophthalmologist or

retinal specialist can develop a customized treatment plan, contributing to a continuously improving learning healthcare system [56].

ROLE OF AI IN DRUG DISCOVERY

Many therapeutic compounds are difficult to create from a chemical environment as a result of inadequate technology. However, this may be resolved by accelerating the drug development process with AI [57]. How that action is and quantitative structure interact affects the way that various parameters, like log P or log D, are forecasted. Through computation, these parameters can be used to produce forecasts and predictions. They can also be used to support side effects, biological safety, and efficacy, as well as the pharmacokinetics of the important molecule [58].

Drug design algorithms consider a lead compound's physical, chemical, and toxicological properties when determining which lead compound to bind with and produce activities [59]. Various physicochemical characteristics can boost biological activity and efficacy [60]. AI-based QSAR techniques maximize QSAR for [61] possible uses as a drug candidate. If the traditional procedures for determining statistical differences are followed, it may take ten years to regulate biological activity that has been discovered and developed [62]. Target receptor binding is influenced by various factors when developing a novel medication, including the drug's solubility, degree of ionization, partition coefficient, and inherent permeability [63]. Algorithms utilize molecular descriptors to forecast the binding properties, such as the Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) [64].

The six physicochemical characteristics that make up the Estimation Program Interface Suite are usually ascertained through utilizing the quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) [65]. Based on the ADMET predictor and ALGOPS software [66], deep learning and neural networks have been employed to forecast the solubility and lipophilicity of different substances. There are multiple undirected graphs used to forecast solubility [67]. Among the variables taken into consideration are surface areas, mass, hydrogen count, refractivity, volume, log P, surface area, and sum of the indices, solubility index, and rotatable bonds when predicting a new chemical entity [68].

ROLE OF AI IN CLINICAL TRIALS

Clinical trial conduct is the most costly and time-consuming step in the drug discovery process. The FDA, or Food and Drug Administration only approve a small percentage of clinical trials, despite the time and money focused to them [69]. Clinical studies may encounter a number of bottlenecks that could cause the experiment to fail. Some of these bottlenecks include a lack of volunteers, trial dropouts, adverse drug reactions, or contradicting data. In the unlikely event that these types of clinical trial fails in a later phase, such as phase III or phase IV [70], the sponsor will bear an exceptionally heavy financial burden.

A further concern is how the costly clinical trials will affect the cost of the patient's therapy in the aftermath. Because of this, biopharma companies factor in when determining the price of approved medications in order to maintain high profit margins, the R&D expenses of unsuccessful studies [71]. The phases involved in carrying out and conducting clinical trials include data collection, analysis, monitoring, patient recruitment and selection, site selection, and trial design. Choosing and recruiting patients is the most time-consuming of these processes

approximately 30% of phase-III trials end prematurely because of problems with patient enrolment and 80% of studies exceed their enrolment schedule. Trial monitoring is an expensive, time-consuming process in a multi-centre global study. Clinical studies are further complicated by the duration of time between the "final subject, final visit" and the data submission—which involves time-consuming data collection and processing procedures to regulatory agencies. Artificial intelligence and digitalization are transforming these clinical trial issues [72].

ROLE OF AI IN VARIOUS EPIDEMICS AND PANDEMICS

Pandemics have no boundaries and can cause both illness and death. The COVID-19 pandemic, the Spanish flu, the Black Death, cholera, influenza, and AIDS [73] are just a few of the many pandemic epidemics that have happened globally. Social and economic structures could be totally destroyed by these plagues. The disease's negative impacts on people's health as well as on political, social, and economic institutions are lessened by early diagnosis and efficient treatment. Monitoring is necessary to accomplish early detection [74].

Time, labour, and resources are all heavily invested in active surveillance. Real-world pandemics and epidemics are unpredictable. But new developments allow us to look into the spread of terrible diseases. Artificial intelligence (AI) is to conduct surveillance while optimizing resource usage is the best option. Numerous healthcare industries are utilizing deep learning and machine learning (ML) because they are more effective than human resources [75].

Because epidemiological models are complex, developing them is still difficult. Recently, models for predicting outbreaks have been created using machine learning [76]. Pandemic and epidemic detection, response, and recovery phases are being handled by AI. With the recent COVID-19 pandemic in mind, prevention is starting to make extensive use of information, prediction, and surveillance [77]. Because influenza epidemics have erratic epidemic peaks, periodic peaking, etc., forecasting one is never easy. A precise forecast can be obtained even in regions where seasonal influenza is unpredictable by incorporating the SAAIM (self-adaptive AI model) [78]. For instance, Taiwan has successfully predicted seasonal influenza using ensemble and machine learning techniques [79]. When it comes to influenza [80], the machine learning feed-forward propagation neural network model (MSDII-FFNN) has an accuracy of 90%. Machine learning anonymized mobility map (AMM) has been used to predict influenza cases in the US and Australia.

By utilizing human movement across state borders, AMM compiles smart phone data to forecast epidemics [81]. The Ebola virus continues to afflict Africa. Numerous methods have been used to forecast the spread of Ebola, such as the hybrid neural network created by Umang Soni et al., which exhibits 100% accuracy in data classification when using random forest [82]. Predicting the propagation has consistently produced consistent results when machine learning is combined with experimental models of artificial communities. For instance, it has been predicted [83] what would happen if researchers looked into how Ebola spread in a Beijing simulation.

Due to the dearth of trustworthy forecasts during the 2015 Zika outbreak, allocating monitoring resources was extremely difficult. Afterwards, the spread was predicted using a dynamic neural network model. Early on in the epidemic, our adaptable predictive model framework proved to be reliable and beneficial [84]. In the Zika project, artificial intelligence neural networks were utilized to detect cases at an early stage [85] and mobile apps were used to track mosquito populations.

The vaccine-derived poliovirus (VDPV) monitoring data have drawn attention. A VDPV epidemic can be predicted by combining the whale optimization algorithm (WOA) with random vector functional link (RVFL) networks in hybrid machine learning [86]. Candidates who are a good fit for pre-exposure prophylaxis in HIV/AIDS prevention initiatives can be identified using machine learning (ML) [87]. A common disease in tropical and subtropical areas is dengue fever. Support vector regression (SVR) [88] is a machine learning technique that can accurately detect and predict dengue outbreaks in China.

Malaysia [89] found that the most accurate dengue predictor was the ML Support vector model (SVM) with a linear kernel. Dengue outbreak predictions were made using Bayesian network machine learning (ML) techniques [90]. The ANN's overall efficacy exceeds 94% when it is integrated with TB suspicious data for quick diagnosis. This will make it possible to determine how the illness is spreading overall and to put some control measures into place in a timely manner [91]. A CNN model called tuberculosis AI (TB-AI) identified TB bacillus with 97.94% sensitivity [92] by utilizing deep learning and machine learning.

The yellow fever diagnosis was attempted with the Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network Classifier (MPNN), which attained 88% prediction accuracy by utilizing the seven psychological symptoms of the illness as a reference [93]. Global shock was caused by the COVID-19 pandemic [94]. The COVID-19 [95] was predicted via AI-inspired modified stacked auto-encoder modelling. The fuzzy rule and deep learning Composite Monte Carlo (CMC) [96] made it simpler to forecast and make decisions regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. The forecast with the lowest amount of error [97] is made using a polynomial neural network with corrective feedback (PNN + CF). In China [98], CNN is utilized, a deep neural network with accurate prediction efficacy. COVID-19 [99] is forecasted in Switzerland using Big Data and the AI model Enerpol. Using statistical and deep learning techniques, such as feed-forward neural networks (FNN), multilayer perception (MLP), autoregressive integrated moving averages (ARIMA), and long short-term memory (LSTM), the dynamic behaviour of COVID-19 was sought after. With regard to the COVID-19 prediction, the information generated might be helpful [100].

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